

Portuguese Accounting Standard 18 - Inventories (IAS 2) A practical approach accounting / auditing

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Abstract: According to NCRF18 - inventories, these "encompass goods purchased and held for resale including, for example, merchandise purchased by a retailer and held for resale, or land and other property held for resale."

As regards the measurement be taken of the available to the NCRF18 establishing that they "shall be measured at cost or net realizable value, whichever is lower."

Note also the complexity of managing the accounting in an industrial company.

As stated Almeida (2017) the area of inventory and biological asset is an area that is of greater importance because of the high mobility (for purchases by the manufacturing process, the sales and by deposits) and because of the risk which is to him associate (slow rotation, breakage, obsolescence, deviations, fraud, etc ..). Also the effect on profitability may be relevant in relation to the size, the time and market value.

Keywords: NCRF 18; Inventories; Shopping; Permanent Stock; Goods

I. NCRF 18 - Accounting

According to the book of instructions from the Portuguese Accounting Order(OCC) - Inventories (2016), the proceed, reserve the Class 3 to make the recognition of inventories and biological assets, and the micro-entities do not use the account of biological assets. In micro entities active biological supplies and agricultural products are recognized as inventories, applying therefore the same rules. The third class of account incorporate assets for all, soon emerge in the balance sheet in current assets and non-current. In current assets, they should be placed accounts that are expected to be carried out over a period up to 12 months after the balance sheet date, or even if they are held for a longer period should be considered as current assets, provided they form part of the normal course the operating cycle (Silva & Martins, 2016). "In the current asset not all be considered asset nature beads whose realization of Class 3 occurs over a period greater than twelve months and that the operating cycle of the entity is not too long" (Silva & Martins, 2016). Included in this type essentially biological assets that are in production-account 372.

According to NCRF18 - inventories, these "encompass goods purchased and held for resale including, for example, merchandise purchased by a retailer and held for resale, or land and other property held for resale. Inventories also encompass finished goods and work in progress that is being produced by the entity and include materials and supplies awaiting use in the production process. Consequently, the common classifications of inventories are merchandise, raw materials, production supplies, materials, work in progress and finished products. In the case of a service provider, inventories, which can be described as work in progress include costs service"

The level 1 of the accounts of the Accounting National System, Class 3 which have to do with Inventories are as follows:

¹ "Norma de Contabilística de Relato Financeiro" - Financial Reporting Standard (Portugal)

- **Account 31 -Purchase** This account records the purchases of goods, raw materials and consumables and biological assets, but also in sub purchases of returns and discounts and rebates on purchases. Thus, this bill is intended formation of the cost of inventories and subsequent transfer to the item to which it relates that purchase, that is, goods, materials and also to biological assets. It is an account that is netted depending on the transfer is made the goods, material or biological active warehouse immediately after the movement of purchase or at the end of the year after physical counts
- **Account 32 - Goods** respect of property acquired by the undertaking to sell, but do not undergo any transformation process;
- **Account 33- Raw materials and consumables;** the raw materials are the goods that are not for sale, but the object of further processing, to be incorporated directly in the manufacture of the final products; the subsidiary materials are property other than being embedded directly in a particular product, contribute to the production also includes the surrounding goods or containers of goods or products are essential to its conditioning and transaction;
- **Account 34 - Finished Products and Intermediate** It includes primarily the goods from productive activity
- **Account 35 - By-products, waste and scrap waste** relates to goods from secondary nature of the production process, as well as those who are not to be regarded as by-products, such as waste and scrap
- **Account 36 - Ongoing products and works** relates to goods which are at an intermediate stage of processing, is expected to be transformed into finished products;
- **Account 37 - biological assets** intended to register the animals and plants alive in the course of farming. Biological assets may be consumable or production
- **Account 38 - Reclassifications** is intended to record the breaks, leftovers, offers, and other variations not derived from purchases, sales or consumption
- **Account 39 - Advances for purchase account** intended to record the purchases of advances with fixed price. If not the case, the advance shall be recorded in an account 22.8 - Advances to suppliers

In addition to these accounts should meet the following accounts:

- **Account 61 - Cost of goods sold and materials consumed** used to register the goods that were consumed during the production process. In the case of adopting the perpetual inventory system, the cost is obtained in a systematic manner, that is, after each operation or set of operations. If you adopt the intermittent inventory system, such cost is only obtained at the end of the period after physical count and subsequent recovery
- **Account 73 - Variation in production inventories** It used to register the variation between the start and end of the period in relation to inventories that are outputs, what means, finished goods, goods and work in progress, by-products, waste, scrap and biological assets

As regards the measurement be taken of the available to the NCRF18 establishing that they "shall be measured at cost or net realizable value, whichever is lower."

The cost of inventories "should include all costs of purchase, costs of conversion and other costs incurred in bringing the inventories to your site and their current condition"

Purchasing costs "include the purchase price, import duties and other taxes (other than those subsequently recoverable from the tax authorities by the organization), and transport, handling and other costs directly attributable to the purchase of goods, materials and services. Trade discounts, rebates and other similar items shall be deducted in determining the costs of purchase. " Thus, they should be valued at cost plus cost of purchasing (transport, insurance, customs costs, etc.) and non-recoverable taxes and less trade discounts and other rebates.

Conversion costs or transformation "include costs directly related to the units of production, such as direct labor. They also include a systematic allocation of fixed production overheads and variables that are incurred in converting materials into finished goods. The overheads are fixed production overhead costs of production that remain relatively constant regardless of the volume of production, such as depreciation and maintenance of factory buildings and equipment and the costs of management and administration of the factory. Overheads production variables are the indirect costs of production that vary directly, or nearly directly, with the volume of production such as indirect materials "

Note that the overheads fixed production attributable to the production costs are only those related to the normal capacity of the production facilities and the amount of overheads allocated to each unit of production is not increased as a result of low production or idle plant. The overheads not allocated are recognized as costs for the year in which they occurred. Accordingly advocates NCRF18 "the allocation of fixed production overheads to the costs of conversion is based on the normal capacity of the production facilities. The normal production capacity is expected to be achieved on average over a number of periods or seasons under normal circumstances, taking into account the loss of capacity resulting from planned maintenance. The actual level of production may be used if it approximates normal capacity. The amount of fixed production overheads allocated to each unit of production is not increased as a consequence of low production or idle plant. The Unallocated overheads are recognized as an expense in the period they are incurred. In periods of abnormally high production, the amount of fixed production overheads allocated to each unit of production is decreased so that inventories are not measured above cost. The variable production overheads are allocated to each unit of production on the basis of actual use of the production facilities " The unallocated overheads are recognized as an expense in the period they are incurred. In periods of abnormally high production, the amount of fixed production overheads allocated to each unit of production is decreased so that inventories are not measured above cost. The variable production overheads are allocated to each unit of production on the basis of actual use of the production facilities "The unallocated overheads are recognized as an expense in the period they are incurred. In periods of abnormally high production, the amount of fixed production overheads allocated to each unit of production is decreased so that inventories are not measured above cost. The variable production overheads are allocated to each unit of production on the basis of actual use of the production facilities"

As stated, Ahmed (2015) the fixed overhead to be charged may be determined as follows:

Fixed overhead chargeable = Total fixed overhead × Actual Production / Normal Production

Standard costs can be used to measure the cost of production, which should take into account normal levels of manpower, supplies and materials, efficiency and capacity utilization. standard costs should be regularly reviewed and updated. The difference between the cost of finished production determined by standard costs and the actual costs of production is recognized in the income statement as expense or income for the period.

It also can be used the retail method where "the cost of inventory is determined by reducing the sales value of the inventory in the appropriate percentage gross margin." This situation occurs "in the retail industry for measuring inventories of large numbers of rapidly changing items, that have similar margins for which it is impracticable to use other costing methods"

Note that "in limited circumstances, borrowing costs are included in cost of inventories. These circumstances are identified in NCRF 10 - Borrowing Costs. " Thus, "the borrowing costs that are directly attributable to the acquisition, construction or production of an asset that qualify are capitalized as part of the cost of that asset, to the extent that it is probable that future economic benefits to the entity and such costs can be measured reliably. " An asset that qualifies "is an asset that necessarily takes a substantial period of time (meaning more than one year) to get ready for its intended use or sale."

With regard to the concept of net realizable value is the estimated selling price in the ordinary course of business less the estimated costs of completion and the estimated costs necessary to make the sale must be confronted with the appropriate cost. It is noted that in the case of finished products and manufacturing routes to be set to the value held liquid, whichever is the lower cost of production. On the other hand, should not be confused with net amount realized fair value. The fair value reflects the amount for which the same inventory could be exchanged between buyers and knowledgeable, willing sellers. The amount realized net is a specific value of an entity, whereas the fair value is no longer.

When the amount resulting from the application of the measurement criteria for the held net value is lower than the recorded value should be accounted for the respective loss impairment, if debiting the account 65.2 - impairment losses in inventory and account 32.9 is crediting (or , according to the case, 33.9 or 34.9 or 35.9) - impairment losses. If it may not justify the reasons that led the losses, it is necessary to the respective reversal (account 76.22 - Reversals inventories)

With respect to biological assets (living plants or animals), the NCRF17 states that "should be measured on initial recognition and at each balance sheet date at their fair value less disposal costs." Should this not be possible, the NCRF provides that "this biological asset should be measured at cost less any accumulated depreciation and any accumulated impairment losses."

Now let us see in brief terms the accounting handling of each inventory account with the respective counterparts debit and credit:

Account 32 -Goods

32 - Goods

Initial Inventory	Discounts
Purchases	Returns
Regularizations	Regularizations
	Cost goods sold
	Final Inventory

Account 33 -Raw materials

33 - Raw Materials

Initial Inventory	Discounts
Purchases	Returns
Regularizations	Regularizations
	Cost goods sold
	Final Inventory

Production account (with the use of analytical accounting/plan).

Production costs are disclosed in the respective control accounts of "materials", "direct labor" and "overheads". The production account balance should be zero at the end of the period. The production that has completed is transferred to the account of finished products and ongoing production existing manufacturing the end of the period the product is transferred to account for manufacturing items.

Production	
Initial Inventory of products being manufactured	finished products
	scrap, waste, etc.
Raw material consumption	Final Inventory of products being manufactured
consumption of direct labor	
consumption of manufacturing overhead	

Account 34 - Finished products (also by extension treatment for waste, waste, etc ..)

34 - Finished Products	
initial inventory of finished products	cost products sold
finished products from production	final inventory of finished products

In financial accounting the initial inventories of finished products, scrap, waste and ongoing are transferred to changes in inventories (account 73) and the respective end inventories also transferred to variations in inventories.

II. Inventories - Audit aspect

As stated Almeida (2017) the area of inventories and biological assets is one of the areas that assumes greater importance because of the high mobility (for purchases by the manufacturing process, the sales and the demand deposits which moves in relation to payments and receipts) and because of the risk associated with it (slow rotation, breakage, obsolescence, deviations, fraud, etc. ..). Also the effect on profitability may be relevant in relation to the size (physical and economic volume and the inherent financial repercussions), time (duration of the production process) and the market value (valuation).

On the other hand, this area is directly related to the other two areas of critical importance to the company: the buying cycle and sales cycle. In industrial companies still assumes importance the connection with personnel expenses and management of tangible fixed assets.

According to Costa & Alves (1999), the main audit objectives to be achieved in the area of inventories are as follows:

- The accounting procedures and internal control measures relating to the inventories and are suitable are, in fact, be applied;
- The quantities in stock represent property inventories of the company and located in its warehouses in third-party warehouse, in transit or on consignment;
- The lists of final inventories are properly compiled and summarized, arithmetically correct and that your total agree with the balances of their accounts;
- Inventories are valued in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles, applied in a manner consistent between years and at the lower of cost or net realized value;
- Excessive or low inventory rotation, defective or damaged, obsolete, etc. .. are covered by adequate impairment;
- The funais inventories are determined in respect of quantity, unit cost calculations, excess inventory, etc., on a consistent basis with those used in previous years;
- The cost of goods sold and materials consumed reflected in the income statement with respect to the period under review and was determined in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles, calculated in a manner consistent with that used in the previous period and is related to the income of inventories recorded in the same period (income spending balancing);
- All relevant information is adequately disclosed in the notes

The stakes are high in this area, and refer to some that are cited by Alves (2015):

- Goods, materials, products manufacturing and finished roads do not exist;
- The goods, materials, products and manufacturing routes finished outside the company;
- Not all goods, materials, products and manufacturing routes have been recorded finished;
- Goods, materials, products manufacturing and finished roads are not included in the financial statements for appropriate amounts and / or there are increases or adjustments not properly registered;
- The financial information relating to goods, materials, products manufacturing and finished way is not properly disclosed and described and disclosures are not clearly expressed.

One of the important factors for the internal control systems evidencing an adaptation to the reality of the company is the existence of the permanent inventory. If the company adopts intermittent inventory does not provide accounting information to enable it to analyze the evolution of the results throughout the year and the value of own inventories. A flashing inventory system always requires the use of global inventories at the year end, with the inconveniences arising therefrom, which are not susceptible to comparison with any accounting records.

The perpetual inventory system, theoretically, should the entity to "all the time" to determine the value of existing inventories in the company. The article. 12 of Decree-Law 158/2009, republished by Law No. 98/2015 which transcribes says:

"The entities to apply the SNC or the international accounting standards adopted by the EU are obliged to adopt the perpetual inventory system in accounting for inventories, as follows.

- a) make the physical inventory counts with reference to the end of the period, or during the period rotatably, so that each well is counted at least once in each period;
- b) Identify the goods in nature, quantity and unit and overall costs in order to allow verification at any time of the correspondence between the physical count and the respective accounting records. "

Thus, the perpetual inventory system allows to know the evolution of the cost of inventory over the period. The inputs and outputs of the stock in the warehouse are recorded in a systematic way, in quantity and value, making it possible to know at all times the inventory accounting position. Otherwise, the purchasing account must always be netted and the cost of goods sold and materials consumed has to be calculated for each sale or consumption. Thus, the accounting permanently reflects²the physical quantities and the respective amount of the existing inventory. Thus, it is possible to know by accounting the value of the stock of goods, raw materials and consumables, finished and intermediate products, goods and work in progress and by-products, waste and scrap, as well as goods sold consumption and consumed raw materials and variations in production inventories³. It notes that competes auditors to obtain an understanding of the accounting system and the control system, carrying out appropriate tests.

Almeida (2017) lists the aspects considered relevant for the internal control systems in the inventory area are effective:

- There must be internal reports related to inventories and cost of goods sold and materials consumed;
- Reports shall be prepared in order to control the costs of purchasing, manufacturing costs, gross margins, obsolete inventories or low turnover, returns and adjustments arising from the realization of counts;
- Reports on the reasonableness of the impairment of inventories;
- Existence of permanent inventory and performing physical counts;
- Suitable control over the documents which support the goods and raw inputs and outputs of finished products and the outputs of goods and products;
- standards of existence on security stocks;
- periodic review by qualified personnel, the cost, the reception of materials and working hours records in each cost center

The auditor shall draw up a work program that will achieve the audit objectives mentioned above, and in particular verify the physical existence of the assets and the actual condition, as well as supporting documentation. This program is due to the knowledge that the auditor has the company, the results previously obtained from other evaluations and interpretation of existing balances.

As indicated in the ISA audit evidence can be obtained by:

- 1) risk assessment procedures; and
- 2) additional audit procedures, which comprise:
 - a) Test checks;
 - b) substantive procedures, including description of tests and analytical procedures

On testing the controls already noted above some that can be used. With regard to the description testing the transactions and balance, the following stand out:

- a) Observation of stocks count - the count is an important procedure as it allows you to check if the items on the inventory list there, and also identify items obsolete, damaged or aged. For this purpose, the auditor keeps

² The official communication 052/15 of the Accounting Standards Board, admits there is flexibility in understanding the accounting reflect constantly as the perpetual inventory system can "be based on accounting extra records, which shall identify goods as to the nature, quantity and unit costs and global susceptible allow control of the correspondence between values of constant registers accounting and values calculated based on physical counts of inventories. " Also there is some flexibility in the understanding of "permanently" to be admitted that "The basis of accounting records in perpetual inventory system does not

is legally established should, in our view, be taken of the nature of activities undertaken by the entity and an analysis of cost effectiveness. "

³ Information obtained on the site <http://www.centralgest.com/centralgest/uploads/Ficheiros/CentralGest-Inventario-Permanente-2016.pdf>, Accessed 3/27/2018

track can perform a random sampling and verify that the goods were properly counted. For the company to have a good permanent inventory system may eventually counts be performed at an earlier date or after the closing of the exercise.

- b) Tests the valuation of inventories - testing the valuation is intended to verify that the inventories are valued in accordance with the rules laid down in the SNC, and in particular with regard to the valuation of inventories and the valuation of warehouse outlets. With regard to outputs NCRF18 establishes the following criteria: specific identification, weighted average cost and FIFO. With regard to the final inventories, as already mentioned, should be valued at the lower of cost and net realizable value, with the net realizable value for finished goods is the selling value less costs to finish and sales. For substances, the replacement cost may be the best way to determine their net realizable value is according to NCR18,
- c) Testing the courts - in order to check is to ensure that all goods received by the closing date were included in the inventory (with the corresponding record in purchases) and that all goods sold excluding inventory form (with the corresponding record in sales), which are registered in the correct period;
- d) valuation of the conversion cost of test - interest here validate the values in the final inventories of finished products and ongoing product and, if the company has prepared the income statement by function, the manufacturing cost of goods sold. The procedures to audit these values do not preclude the analysis of the costs with the consumption of materials, of labor, direct labor and manufacturing overheads allocated through the normal activity which is the recommended procedure for NCRF18;
- e) Test property - interests here validate that there are in the warehouse on consignment goods, goods that belong to third parties and may also occur the opposite situation, company assets that are in third party warehouses.

With regard to the procedures can be calculated a number of indicators expressing the economic and financial development of the company. Among all indicators (ratios) we can be highlighted as follows:

<i>ratio</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Inventory of goods / goods sold Cost x 360	Measures the length of stay of the goods in the warehouse (days)
Inventories Raw Material / Cost Consumed x 360	Measures the time spent materials in storage (days)
Inventories Finished Products / Cost Selling Products x 360	Measure the residence time of the finished product in storage (days)
Gross Margin / Turnover	Measures the gross margin as a percentage of turnover
Accumulated impairment / Inventories	Measuring the level of inventory problems (obsolete, hard placement, etc ..) in total inventories
Production of Finished Cost / Quantity Produced	Measure the unit cost of the finished products
Cost of Goods Sold / Quantity Sold	Measures the unit cost of goods sold
Cost of Goods Sold / Quantity Sold	Measures the cost of goods sold

Table 1: Ratios Audit Inventories

Source: Prepared by the authors

This analysis ratios should be made compared to the same ratios from previous periods, with the budget values, if any, with the sector.

For example fluctuations in gross margin may indicate that inventories are not properly valued or purchases or sales were made that were not recorded in the correct period. Also different values from period to period may also indicate possible cases of fraud.

With regard to the permanence ratios, fluctuations may indicate excess or lack of goods in inventory, changes in accounting methods, etc. Also values upward trend may indicate that the company is having difficulty disposing of their goods / products.

With regard to fluctuations in costs, it is interested behavior analysis of production costs with particular emphasis on the weight of materials, hand labor and general manufacturing costs in the final price.

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